

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS TO SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract. *This scientific article talks about the role of innovative education in the teaching of mathematics. The formation of educational innovative principles, modern methods of improving education through effective use are shown in it. With the demands of our time, it is necessary to use innovative technologies to make mathematics lessons more interesting.*

Keywords: *method, "Ball exercise", "Train" exercise, "Relay" exercise, innovative technologies, modern teaching methodology.*

Life itself shows that the power of every country is determined, first of all, by the education system. Interest and attention to the use of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. The main reason for this is that until today, on the basis of traditional education, we taught students to acquire knowledge only on the basis of questions and answers, but on the basis of innovative technologies, they are now searching for new knowledge on their own, along with acquiring knowledge. On the basis of technologies innovative in the mathematics lesson, students find the answers to examples and problems in an easy way, independently analyze them, and even create new similar examples and problems. For example, the interactive method of brainstorming. This training is mainly conducted among group members. The process is useful for generating creative thoughts and ideas. Brainstorming helps students learn to work together. You'll be amazed at all the great ideas they come up with.

"Practice with a ball". The main part: Students understand how important intelligence, resourcefulness are in performing this exercise. They get information about the exercise. Students understand how important intelligence, resourcefulness, resourcefulness are in performing this exercise. They get information about the exercise.

Execution of the exercise: students are divided into 2 groups, ask each other questions and throw balls. The student who caught the ball answers the question. He also asks questions and passes the ball to another student. The questions are related to the topic or off-topic.

"Grapes are ripe, enter the garden" game technology. It is recommended to play this game in small groups. A "Grape" market is distributed to each group. Grapes are "cooked" based on the assignment on the grape leaf. Pupils write examples of grapes. The group that completes the task correctly and quickly will be the winner.

"Relay" exercise. These exercises can be performed as a competition, for example, writing words on a blackboard, reciting a poem, or rolling a ball or a wheel from the beginning to the end of the desk. These exercises are interesting, full of action, and the students will be happy by the end of the exercise.

"Train" exercise. Students get out of their desks and line up. The next step: students walk along the corridors between the desks one after the other, like a train. For the students, when it is

said "We are going as a train, we will divide into three corners" when they are walking as a "train", they should stand up in 3 directions. Pupils who are left behind or cannot be divided into corners sit in their seats. This movement exercise improves the brain activity of students and raises their mood. Increases efficiency and cohesion. As we have seen, mobile methods serve as an action that increases the quality and efficiency of the student's mastery of the subject, the result expected by the teacher. In the course of the lesson, mobile interactive methods create the following qualities in students. It raises the mood movement methods help the student master the subject, strengthen memory, develop brain activity, improve blood circulation, quickly learn new things, ingenuity and sensitivity arise. The quality and efficiency of education increases.

Using the didactic capabilities of text and table editors in creating pedagogical tools for skills related to the skillful use of modern information communication tools in education. In addition, this methodology involves knowing in which part of the lesson and for how long the ICT tools will be used.

In the course of the lesson, the teacher increases the interest of the students in the lessons on the basis of pedagogical technologies and delivers them using pedagogical technologies and videos. In education aimed at developing the student's personality, it is the student's pedagogical skill that is of great importance. In the implementation of person-oriented education, the teacher should be perfect in organizing the pedagogical environment adapted to the students, at least in the educational process. In particular, creating an environment of success in education, helping the child to succeed in studies, gaining confidence in his own strength and talent and letting him know that everyone around him is like him, developing a sense of belonging to the team, student's respect and it is very important to gain his trust, to look at himself as a person, to respect, respect and trust each student. Therefore, the education aimed at the development of the student's personality takes into account the mental, emotional, physical, moral and spiritual growth of the child, his interests, intellectual, physical, moral and spiritual growth. According to today's requirements, the teacher skillfully organizes the lesson process, makes it easier, simpler, or more complicated according to the program based on the situation, affects the students' morale, pays attention to their health. should give physical, moral and spiritual growth. According to today's requirements, the teacher skillfully organizes the lesson process, makes it easier, simpler, or more complicated according to the program based on the situation, affects the students' morale, pays attention to their health. should give physical, moral and spiritual growth. According to today's requirements, the teacher skillfully organizes the lesson process, makes it easier, simpler, or more complicated according to the program based on the situation, affects the students' morale, pays attention to their health. should give

In short, the modern teacher should be able to form skills such as cooperation in the use of ICT, solving problems, searching for knowledge, analyzing and summarizing information from different sources from a critical point of view.

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